

Bending behaviour of non-rigid connected steel-timber composite beams - An experimental and numerical parametric study

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ABSTRACT

Combining cross-laminated timber (CLT) with steel girders using a shear connection represents an innovative and sustainable alternative for highly loaded concrete or composite slabs for spans larger than 8 metres. The achievable composite effect between steel and CLT depends on the stiffness of the shear connection. The load-bearing behaviour of fully threaded screws and shear studs cast into CLT-openings has already been analysed in push-out tests.

Based on this, CLT steel composite beams with different cross-sectional configurations and the above-mentioned shear connectors were investigated in 4-point bending tests in spans of 8.10 metres up to 10.8 metres. After a distinct linear-elastic deformation process, the steel girder deformed strongly plastically until tensile failure of the CLT starts. The tests validated numerical models from 3D finite elements with a high degree of accuracy. Numerical parameter studies were performed to investigate the influences of the stiffness and the spacing of the shear-connectors, the number and the dimension of the CLT-layers, as well as the stiffness properties of CLT. The number of layers of the CLT, as well as moderate variations in shear modulus of the transverse layers, showed only a limited influence on the composite bending stiffness. In addition to the general stiffness of the shear connection, the spacing of the shear connectors at a constant stiffness of the composite connection per metre strongly affected the composite bending stiffness.

Generally, the results proof that the efficiency of CLT composite beams depend significantly on the ratio of the dimensions of both cross-sections, as well as stiffness and spacing of the shear connectors.

Keywords: Steel-timber composite, composite bending behaviour, Finite element method

1 INTRODUCTION

A CLT-steel composite beam (*Fig. 1*) allows extending the application range of CLT to floors with larger spans and higher loads. Due to the flexibility of the fasteners and the shear deformation of the transverse layers of the CLT, the load-bearing behaviour of a CLT-steel-composite beam differs from that of a concrete-steel composite beam. Hassanieh et al. (1), (2) and Loss et al. (3) developed various shear connecting systems using screws, bolts, toothed plates, nail plates, steel components or gluing and investigated them in push-out tests. Based on this, Hassanieh et al. studied the bending performance of composite beams made of steel girders and CLT or laminated veneer lumber in experimental and numerical 4-point bending tests with spans of 3 to 6 m with varying shear connectors (4) (5). Loss et al. also carried out experimental and numerical bending tests on CLT-steel composite beams with spans of about 6 m with U- and Ω -formed steel with glued-in perforated plates and vertically inclined screws (6) (7). Merryday et al. (8) carried out a larger-format 4-point bending test on members with a span of 9.14 m with a narrow CLT element of a width of 0.483 m. Both Hassanieh et al. and Loss et al. modelled the steel and the timber numerically considering non-linear material behaviour with 2D and 3D elements.

The above-mentioned works on the bending behaviour and the numerical modelling of CLT-steel-composite beams were mainly limited to shorter spans up to about 6 m, thinner CLT with a maximum of five layers and a continuous arrangement of shear connectors. The influence of continuously and discontinuously arranged shear connectors and the influence of the rolling shear deformation of the transverse layers on the elastic bearing capacity for spans over 8 m needs to be assessed. 15 large-scale tests were carried out at our laboratory. The investigations are based on previous studies on the load-bearing behaviour of inclined fully threaded screws and shear studs as shear connectors (9).

This work presents the results of the experimental and numerical investigations of the short-term performance of CLT-steel composite beams with spans between 8 and 11 m and of a parametric study.

Fig. 1. CLT-steel composite beam

2 EXPERIMENTAL BENDING TESTS

2.1 Test programme

Prior to the numerical investigations, five different test series were conducted. The first test series (C1.1) represents the basic configuration. A composite beam, 8.10 m span, consisting of a five-layered CLT200 element with a width of 1.50 m and a steel section HEA 200 was tested in bending. Fully threaded screws were used as shear connectors. The screws were installed at an angle $\alpha = 45^\circ$ in the vertical plane and at an angle of $\beta = 30^\circ$ in the horizontal plane. In the subsequent test series, one parameter (span, cross-sectional structure and shear connectors) was varied in each case.

Table 1. Test programme of the experimental bending tests

Test series	Quantity	Span	CLT	Steel	Shear connectors
C1.1	3	8.10 m	CLT200 L5s	HEA200 S355	Fully threaded screws $\varnothing 10 \times 155$ mm
C1.2	3	10.8 m	CLT200 L5s	HEA200 S355	Fully threaded screws $\varnothing 10 \times 155$ mm
C1.3	3	8.10 m	CLT240 L7s	HEA160 S355	Fully threaded screws $\varnothing 10 \times 155$ mm
C1.4	3	10.8 m	CLT240 L7s	HEA160 S355	Fully threaded screws $\varnothing 10 \times 155$ mm
C2.1	3	8.10 m	CLT200 L5s	HEA200 S355	Cast-in Shear studs $\varnothing 22 \times 90$ mm

2.2 Test setup

The tests were based on the specifications according to EN 408 (10) and EN 16351 (11). The preloading procedure was adapted from previous bending tests of Hassanieh et al. (5). The tests were conducted as 4-point bending tests with an excess end of 40 cm on both hinged supports. The load was initially force-controlled up to a preload of 40 % of the estimated maximum load. After a holding time of 30 seconds, unloading to 10 % of the estimated maximum load, the main load was applied until failure or a deformation of 210 mm, limited by the stroke of the jack. The loading was applied displacement-controlled at 5 mm/min. As shown in Fig. 2, the vertical deflections at midspan and under the load application points, as well as the horizontal slip in the composite connection at supports and quarter points were monitored with displacement transducers. The strains at the lower and upper

flanges and web of the steel girder, as well as the lower and upper side of the CLT were measured at mid- and quarter span by means of strain gauges.

Fig. 2. Test set-up and measuring technique of the four-point bending tests

2.3 Material Properties

CLT elements from HBS Berga (ETA-20/0860) were made of spruce wood grade C24. The CLT elements in test series C1.1, C1.2 and C2.1 had the layer-structure 40l-40q-40l-40q-40l, while those in series C1.3 and C1.4 had the layer-structure 40l-30q-40l-20q-40l-30q-40l. A moisture content of $9,8 \% \pm 0,5 \%$ was measured for all CLT elements. The steel girders were HEA160 and HEA200 sections made of steel grade S355JR. The properties of CLT and steel were investigated in additional material tests and are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Material properties of CLT

	f_m	$f_{c,0}$	$f_{t,0}$	E_0	
Mean value	36.6	28.3	20.0	12,774	N/mm ²
5% quantile	26.0	20.2	16.1	10.443	N/mm ²

Table 3. Material properties of steel

	f_u	f_y	E_t	E	
Mean value	557.2	395.3	1,414.1	209,585	N/mm ²

2.4 Results

In all test series, the deformation of the composite beams was linear elastic until the yield strength of the steel. The plastification starts at 70 to 76 % of the maximum test load. With a further load increase, the steel deforms plastically until a tensile failure at the underside of the CLT occurs. In Table 4, the elastic limit load F_y and the corresponding deflection w at midspan and the slip v of the composite connection at the supports are given. These are average values for each test series.

The screws used in the test series C1.1 to C1.4 deformed elastically. Due to the constant composite connection stiffness, the shear force was transferred continuously between the materials during the elastic deformation. As visible in Fig. 3 (left), the vertical deflection w is approximately a bilinear curve with a transition region at the steel yield point. For test series C2.1 a different behaviour is observed, namely a trilinear load-deflection characteristics (Fig. 3, right). This is caused by the deformation of the shear studs used in C2.1. At about 30 % of the maximum test load, the mortar around the shear studs cracked and the stiffness of the connection was thus reduced. However, under further loading the cracked mortar is confined by the surrounding CLT. Consequently, a constant, but lower stiffness can still be achieved. Further test results and analyses can be found in (12).

Table 4. Elastic maximum load F_y and corresponding midspan deflection w and horizontal slip v at support

Test series	Span	Configuration	F_y [kN]	w [mm]	v [mm]
C1.1	8.10 m	CLT200 L5s + HEA200	214.48	85.78	2.97
C1.2	10.8 m	CLT200 L5s + HEA200	149.36	125.24	2.01
C1.3	8.10 m	CLT240 L7s + HEA160	258.33	100.68	3.42
C1.4	10.8 m	CLT240 L7s + HEA160	159.41	138.67	2.44
C2.1	8.10 m	CLT200 L5s + HEA200	209.64	105.35	5.63

Fig. 3. Load deflection curve for the deflection w at midspan for test series C1.1 and C2.1

3 NUMERICAL MODELLING

3.1 Modelling principles

The tests were modelled using ANSYS Workbench 2023 and validated using the mean test results. The steel girder and the individual layer of the CLT were idealised with 3D solid elements using a quadratic attachment function. The steel was modelled with 10-node tetrahedral elements (SOLID 187) and the CLT with 20-node hexagonal elements (SOLID186), with a mesh size of 100 mm. The CLT was not divided into individual lamellas, but into layers. Adaptive mesh refinements were made during the calculation. The glued contacts of the layers were assumed to be rigid. The steel was defined using a bilinear stress-strain constitutive law. Until the yield strength f_y , the gradient of the stress-strain curve was defined by the modulus of elasticity E . The subsequent elastic-plastic range up to tensile strength f_u was also defined in simplified form by a constant strain-hardening modulus E_t . The timber was assumed fully elastic with a constant modulus of elasticity. The timber lamellae were defined as an elastic-orthotropic material with different stiffness and strengths properties in longitudinal, tangential and radial directions. The main axis was rotated by 90° between the longitudinal and transverse layers. The parameters were determined in small-format material tests from the composite beams and are shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

The contact surface between the CLT and the steel was assumed as not shear-connected and in accordance with Owolabi et al. (7), friction effects were neglected. The composite forces were only transferred via the shear connectors, each of them was modelled by a single spring. The spring stiffness was defined as the horizontal stiffness of the shear connectors. As the screws deformed only elastically, a constant slip modulus of 8500 kN/m per screw from double push-out tests (9) could be assumed for the spring stiffness. Due to the early cracking of the mortar around the shear studs, a non-linear spring deformation was defined with COMBIN39 elements for these connectors. The stiffness was idealised with the simplified load-slip curve of the shear studs from the double push-out tests in (9) and is shown per shear stud in Fig. 5 on the right.

Fig. 4. FE model of test specimen C1.3 with meshing

Fig. 5. Screws as linear springs (left), simplified load-slip curve of the shear studs as non-linear springs (right)

3.2 Validation of the numerical models

To validate the numerical models, the vertical deflection w at midspan and the horizontal slip v in the composite connection at the support were compared first. The deformations of the bending tests were compared with those of the numerical models at the elastic limit load, as shown in Table 5. Test series C1.1 could be numerically reproduced with an error of less than 1 %. In all test series, the deflection w and the slip v at this load level were met very well with a maximum deviation of 8 %. Only the slip v in the composite connection in test series C2.1 showed greater scatter due to cracking in the mortar and could be modelled with an accuracy of 12 %. The deformations could also be reproduced for the entire elastic bearing range using the numerical models.

Table 5. Midspan deflection w and horizontal slip v at support at elastic limit load of experimental and numerical tests

Test series	Span	Configuration	F_y [kN]	Experimental results		Numerical results	
				w [mm]	v [mm]	w [mm]	v [mm]
C1.1	8.10 m	CLT200 L5s + HEA200	214.48	85.78	2.97	86,09	2,97
C1.2	10.8 m	CLT200 L5s + HEA200	149.36	125.24	2.01	125,07	2,17
C1.3	8.10 m	CLT240 L7s + HEA160	258.33	100.68	3.42	108,44	3,38
C1.4	10.8 m	CLT240 L7s + HEA160	159.41	138.67	2.44	134,92	2,34
C2.1	8.10 m	CLT200 L5s + HEA200	209.64	105.35	5.63	98,60	4,93

The normal stress curves under the elastic limit load are compared below. In both cases only the edge strains were measured and transformed into stress using the measured moduli of elasticity (Table 2, Table 3); the intermediate values were interpolated. The normal stresses in the transverse layers of the CLT were neglected as these were below 0.5 N/mm^2 . The numerical models can reproduce the normal stresses of the bending tests very well. The validation for the elastic deformation is thus sufficiently accurate. The small deviations could have been caused by scattering of the modulus of elasticity of timber, the yield strength of the steel and the stiffness of the shear connectors, as well as the idealised material models. A change in the material properties did not reduce the deviations

between bending tests and models across all test series. Increasing the modulus of elasticity of timber, for example, led to lower deflections, lower normal stress in steel and higher normal stresses in timber. As with reduction in the modulus of elasticity, no constant approximation to the test values was achieved across all test series. The material properties determined in material tests therefore appear to be suitable on average and only the individual scattering is the reason for the deviations.

Fig. 6. Normal stress curve at midspan from test results (red) and numerical models (blue) under elastic limit load for each test series (Stress in the CLT shown ten times enlarged)

4 NUMERICAL PARAMETRIC STUDY

Various factors influencing the load-bearing behaviour of the composite beams were investigated in a parametric study based on the validated FE-models. The results are presented below.

4.1 Shear modulus and Young modulus perpendicular to the plane of the CLT

Non-rigid connected beams can be designed using the γ -method (EN 1995-1-1 Annex B). The calculation follows the principle of the rigid composite theory, whereby the inertia component of Steiner's theorem is reduced γ -fold for one cross-section, depending on the shear connector stiffness. If the bending stiffness of the CLT-steel composite beam is calculated using the γ -method, the shear deformations of the shear connectors, but not of the CLT are considered. Table 6 shows the bending stiffness according to the γ -method (row 1), neglecting the shear deformations of the CLT, and the bending stiffness under a line load from the validated numerical models (row 2). The results of the γ -method and the numerical calculation differ significantly, as the shear deformation of the transverse layers of the CLT was not considered in the γ -method. To check whether the deviation between the numerical and analytical calculations was solely due to the shear deformations of the timber, the bending stiffness was recalculated numerically (Table 6, row 3) with shear-rigid timber ($G_A = G_{RA} = \infty$). The bending stiffness determined numerically and validated with test results is still lower than calculated analytically, even if the shear deformations are neglected in both calculations. The deviation only occurs if the timber is modelled as 3D elements and the stiffness rectangular to the panel plane is considered. The modelling with 2D elements shows analogous results to the γ -method, but then with consideration of the shear deformations also clear deviations from the test results.

Table 6. Elastic bending stiffness according to the gamma method and the numerical models

	C1.1	C1.2	C1.3	C1.4
γ -method	30,157 kNm ²	34,268 kNm ²	32,172 kNm ²	35,675 kNm ²
FEM	25,464 kNm ²	30,178 kNm ²	24,527 kNm ²	30,015 kNm ²
FEM ($G_A = G_{RA} = \infty$)	27,329 kNm ²	31,956 kNm ²	26,410 kNm ²	31,883 kNm ²

4.2 Stiffness of the composite connection

The stiffness of the shear connectors has a significant influence on the composite effect. For test series C1.1 and C1.3, the bending stiffness and the degree of composite action were determined for the stiffness of the composite connection of 85,000 kN/m of the actual test configuration. In a second step, both values were determined for other composite connection stiffnesses. The results are shown in Table 7. In test series C1.1 and C1.3, degrees of composite action of 53 % and 54 % were achieved with ten screws per metre. As expected, a reduction in the composite connection stiffness leads to a lower, while an increase leads to a higher composite bending stiffness. With stiffer CLT, as in C1.3, more shear force must be transferred through the composite connection, so that the connectors deform more. This leads to higher deformations in the composite connection. In order to achieve an equivalent degree of composite action above 65 %, a significantly higher composite connection stiffness and thus more shear connectors are required in C1.3 with more massive CLT than in C1.1.

Table 7. Bending stiffness and degree of composite action for different composite connection stiffnesses

Composite connection stiffness [kN/m]	0	21,250	85,000	340,000	1,360,000	5,440,000	∞
C1.1 Bending stiffness EI [kNm ²]	16,040	20,070	25,268	29,972	32,312	32,952	33,520
Degree of composite action μ [%]	0	23	53	80	93	97	100
C1.3 Bending stiffness EI [kNm ²]	17,022	20,517	24,729	28,096	29,477	29,882	31,343
Degree of composite action μ [%]	0	24	54	77	87	90	100

4.3 Spacing of the shear connectors

The same composite connection stiffness per metre can be achieved by arranging a few very stiff shear connectors or several less stiff shear connectors. The spacing of the shear connectors affects the bending stiffness. That is why a continuous shear connection is a precondition of the gamma method in Eurocode 5 for determining the bending stiffness of composite beams. A continuous arrangement means a sufficiently small spacing between every connector. Rautenstrauch et al. (13) limit the maximum spacing of the shear connectors to 3 % of the span. Larger spacings must be considered as discontinuous arrangement, which lead to a significantly change of the load-bearing capacity.

The effects of the spacing were initially investigated using the numerical model of test series C1.1. For investigation of this model, two adjacent rows of springs with a stiffness of 8,500 kN/m at a distance of 20 cm along the beam axis were used. Ten springs per metre of beam length resulted in a total connection stiffness of 85,000 kN/m. The spacing of the shear connectors was 2.5 % of the span. The spacing of the shear connectors was then varied within a range of 1% to 50 % of the span. The spring stiffnesses were adjusted so that the overall stiffness of the composite connection always remained constant. Subsequently, the same spacing were analysed for the 0.25, 0.5, 2 and 4-fold stiffness levels. The same configurations were investigated for test series C1.2 and C1.3 to check the changes for other spans (C1.2 with $l = 10.80$ m) and other cross-sectional configurations (C1.3).

Fig. 7 shows the change in bending stiffness depending on the spring spacing normalised to the span. Five different connection stiffness levels are shown for each test configuration. Each test configuration has a colour. The stiffness levels of the composite connection are marked with different brightnesses of the colour of the test series.

The composite bending stiffness decreases for both spans, both cross-sections and all composite connection stiffnesses between 21,250 kN/m and 340,000 kN/m with increasing connector spacing. Using the continuous spacing (1 % of the span) as a reference value, the bending stiffness is reduced

by up to 3 % for a spacing of 2.5 % of the span, up to 6 % for a spacing of 5 % of the span and up to 20 % for a large spacing. With a high stiffness of the composite connection (graphs with dark shades), increasing the shear connector spacing while maintaining the same connection stiffness led to a greater decrease in the composite bending stiffness. The bending stiffness continued to change even at large spacing. With a lower stiffness (graphs with light shades) of the composite connection, the bending stiffness changed for spacing up to 5 % - 10 % of the span and then remained nearly constant. Increasing shear connector spacing led to higher normal stresses in both materials at midspan and greater horizontal slip in the composite connection at the support. The described behaviours occurred equally in the test series with different cross-section configurations and different spans.

Fig. 7. Dependency of the composite bending stiffnesses on the spacing of the shear connectors for different composite connection stiffnesses and test series

4.4 Number and rolling shear stiffness of the transverse layers of the CLT

Only the layers whose fibres run parallel to the load direction contribute significantly to the bearing capacity. The transverse layers only connect the longitudinal layers. The shear deformation due to the low rolling shear modulus reduces the bending stiffness of the CLT and therefore also the composite bending stiffness. The impact of the shear deformation depends on the number and the thickness of the transverse layers and the value of the rolling shear modulus. The effect of the layer structure of the CLT is analysed using the configuration of test series C1.1 with a five layered CLT. The configuration is compared with two composite beams whose CLT have the same thickness of 20 cm, but one has seven and the other nine layers. The layer thicknesses were selected so that all configurations (5, 7, and 9 layered) have the same bending and axial stiffnesses. The rolling shear modulus in the numerical models is 50 N/mm². At this level, the composite bending stiffness was about 0.5 % lower for 7 layers and 2 % lower for 9 layers than for 5 layers. With a higher rolling shear modulus, the differences increased by up to 2 % for 7 layers and 4 % for 9 layers. With a low rolling shear modulus, a higher number of layers did not lead to a lower composite bending stiffness. Apparently, the value of the rolling shear modulus is also decisive. Therefore, the composite bending stiffness was calculated numerically for the three above mentioned configurations for different rolling shear modules, as well as for the test series C1.3 with thicker CLT.

Fig. 8 shows the composite bending stiffnesses of the four configurations as a function of the rolling shear modulus. For a rolling shear modulus above 100 N/mm², the change in composite bending stiffness is less than 1 % for a doubled rolling shear modulus. From then on, a rigid composite can be assumed. From a rolling shear modulus of 50 N/mm², used in the bending tests, to 100 N/mm², the composite bending stiffness increases by 1 % to 3 %. If the actual rolling shear modulus (50 N/mm²) is halved, the composite bending stiffness is reduced by up to 5 %. At values lower than 25 N/mm², the composite bending stiffness decreases quadratically and approaches the value without composite. The number of layers and the thickness of the CLT have a slight influence on the curvature of the graphs in the area around a rolling shear modulus of 50 N/mm². The higher the number of layers, the smaller the transition area between quasi-rigid and strongly decreasing composite bending stiffness.

Fig. 8. Dependency of the composite bending stiffness on the rolling shear modulus of timber

5 CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn from the test results and the validated numerical models:

- Using a linear-elastic timber material model is sufficient to numerically simulate the elastic load-bearing behaviour of CLT-steel composite beams. Since the steel usually plastifies before timber failure, a multi-linear stress-strain relation should be defined for the steel.
- The shear connectors may be idealised as linear-elastic springs if they are not stressed to their limit load. Defining non-linear springs using simplified load-slip curve from push-out tests is sufficiently accurate to reproduce shear connectors exceeding their elastic limits or cracking.
- The screw configuration used in the tests enables a degree of composite action of 50 % to 51 % for a span of 8.1 m. A realistic improvement for the screws seems to be a doubling at the maximum, which could further improve the degree of composite action by around 15 %. Degrees of composite action above 80 % are not achievable with pure screw connections.
- The comparison of the γ -method and the numerical models shows that, in addition to the shear deformation of the shear connectors and the CLT, the timber stiffness perpendicular to the panel plane also has a significant influence on the composite bending stiffness.
- A continuous shear connection can be assumed up to a maximum spacing of the connectors of 3 % of the span, as formulated for the gamma-method, as otherwise the discontinuous arrangement consecutively leads to a lower bending stiffness. Spacings greater than 3 % of the span must be considered directly calculating the bending stiffness or the normal stresses.
- Increasing the spacing between the connectors while maintaining the same connection stiffness per metre reduces the composite effect and thus leads to lower material efficiency.

- With same thickness, bending and axial stiffnesses of the pure CLT, a higher number of layers with a rolling shear modulus above 25 N/mm² leads to a slight decrease in the composite bending stiffness. The deviations are limited and are negligible in practical application.
- For a rolling shear modulus between 25 and 100 N/mm², which is relevant for the practical application of CLT with spruce, the composite bending stiffness varies by up to 8 %.

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